
**ABUNDANCE AND DIVERSITY OF INSECTS IN BORIKIRI MANGROVE ECOSYSTEM IN
NIGER DELTA, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The diversity of insects in Borikiri mangrove habitat along the Bonny River was investigated for three months (April–June, 2017). The study was carried out to establish a basic understanding of the diversity pattern of insect assemblages in the area and to understand the relationship between the surrounding mangrove ecosystem and associated insect fauna. Two mangrove plant species were investigated: *Rhizophora* and *Avicennia* species. A total of 6 insect orders, Diptera, Coleoptera, Hymenoptera, Homoptera, Orthoptera, Odonata, 24 families and 42 species were identified and recorded. This study shows that Diptera (73%) was the highest insect order recorded, followed by Hymenoptera 9% and Coleoptera 7%. The highest insect diversity was observed on *Avicennia* in Hemiptera (Shannon's, $H' = 2.87$), while Orthoptera and Coleoptera (Shannon's, $H' = 0.00$) were the lowest. However, on *Rhizophora*, Coleoptera and Hymenoptera had the highest Shannon value of 1.74 while Hemiptera and Odonata (Shannon's, $H' = 0.00$) were the lowest. The highest insect richness was observed on *Rhizophora* in Orthoptera (Margalef index, = 0.72) and the highest insect evenness was observed on *Rhizophora* in Hymenoptera and Coleoptera (Evenness, $E = 0.79$). Results of the present study will eventually contribute to biodiversity conservation and management of ecosystems in the Niger Delta. More studies on the diversity of insects in mangrove ecosystems within the Niger delta area are encouraged.

Key words: Mangrove ecosystem, insect biodiversity, forest, Borikiri, Niger Delta, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Insects constitute the major component of animal diversity in most habitats and ecosystems (Ananthaselvi *et al.*, 2009). They are the largest group and in terms of diversity, the most diverse and constitutes more than half of the world animal species (Aslam, 2009). Speight *et al.* (2008) observed that insects are the most populated organisms in the world, because different species reproduce fast and have enormous numbers of offspring; some do not even care for their young.

They can adapt to nearly all environments, but only a few species stay in the oceans (Nandini and Murali, 2012). They are highly sensitive to changes in climatic factors, such as rainfall, temperatures, wind, humidity and altitudes (Khaliq *et al.*, 2014) as these affect their population dynamics, distribution, abundance, intensity and feeding behavior (Ayres and Schneider, 2009).

Insects are important components in most natural and transformed landscapes. They play crucial functional roles that ensure delivery of various ecosystem services which are important for some aspects of human livelihood such as agriculture, tourism and natural resource use (Tscharntke *et al.*, 2005). They also control populations of other organisms, serve as the major food source for other taxa (Majer, 1987), and are useful as bio-indicator of fresh water bodies (Okoro, 2015). However, they are also disease vectors to several organisms, including humans, and they have the capacity to alter the rates and directions of energy and matter fluxes in an ecosystem (Schowalter, 2010). Gbadegesin *et al.* (1999) report that majority of the insects feed on all kinds of plants including forest nursery seedlings, crop plants, forest trees, and weeds on the field, thus modifying the range condition of the ecosystem.

However, Despite their important economic role, a huge number of insects are declining globally and are going into extinction (Balakrishnan *et al.*, 2014) due to habitat fragmentation and degradation as well as indiscriminate bush burning and overgrazing which lead to habitat destruction that has consequent impact on insect species (Emma-Okafor, 2011).

Disappearance of insects could lead to extinction of earth's animals because of the disappearance of so much plant life. Today insects are by far the planet's most diverse, abundant and successful species (Zrzavy, 2008). The roles (positive or negative) insects play in nature require proper understanding on how they interact with living and non-living environment and their diversity (Miller, 2006). The aim of the present investigation is to survey the taxonomic status, composition and abundance of insects in Borikiri mangrove ecosystem along the Bonny River.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Borokiri is a neighborhood of the city of Port Harcourt and is situated south of the old government residential area with coordinates 4°44'56"N, 7°2'6"E. The neighborhood is bounded by Ahoada Street to the north; Okirika Island to the east; Orubiri oilfield to the south and Ship Builders Road to the west and is under the Port Harcourt city Local Government Area. The prevailing climatic conditions of Port Harcourt overlap on this neighborhood as well as in the other two study areas. The major drainage pattern around Port Harcourt is largely controlled by the Bonny River, its tributaries and creek. The mangrove species at the site is dominated by *Rhizophora mangle*, and a few stands of *Rhizophora racemosa*, *Avicennia africana* and *Laguncularia racemosa*. The study area is bordered by a variety of built-up land cover serving commercial and residential purposes. Within the mangrove area anthropogenic factors and activities have led to loss of vast portions that are deforested preparatory for low cost housing development and other projects.

Plant species sampled

The plant species sampled for the study were members of *Rhizophora* and *Avicennia*. The reason for choosing these two plant species was based on their abundance in the study area, as well as the impact of anthropogenic activities resulting into their depletion.

Sampling procedure

Samples were collected biweekly during the dry season for three months, April, May and June, 2017. Two sampling stations were established based on the abundance of the plant species sampled. For each station, transect line range 90 meters was laid perpendicular to the shore line. Within the transect line, 10 by 10 m plots for the sampling of mangrove trees with an interval of twenty (20) meters between each plot were set up in each station. Three 10x10 m plots were laid and three (3) trees were sampled in each plot, making it nine (9) for each sample station and eighteen (18) trees for both sampling stations. A total of one hundred and eight (108) trees were sampled within the study window. Each tree was sampled for ten (10) minutes.

Sampling of insects was done in the morning between 7am and 11am at low tide, when most insects were very active. At each plot, insects were collected from the randomly selected trees using sweep nets, hand nets, hand picking methods and also by taking photographs of insects and noting down plant on which the insect was observed (Rahaman, 2002). All insects collected were placed into a small vial, properly labeled and preserved in 70% ethanol for identification.

Identification of insects

All samples collected from the study areas were identified according to Ameen *et al.*, (1982) and Ameen and Nessa (1985). Validation of identified insects was also carried out at the Insect Museum, Department of Crop Protection, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.

Statistical analysis

Biodiversity indices were calculated using standard formulae. Diversity of insect species found on both *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora* was calculated using two diversity (Shannon Wiener diversity H' and Margalef diversity index R) and Evenness indices (Pielou Evenness (J')).

$$H = -\sum[(pi) \times \ln(pi)]$$

SUM = summation pi = proportion of total sample represented by species

$$R = (S - 1) / \log_{10} N$$

Where R = Margalef index, S = the number of species and N = the total number of individuals.

$$\text{Evenness} = E = H / \ln(S)$$

Where H' is Shannon Weiner diversity and S is the total number of species in a sample, across all samples in dataset.

These analyses and graphical representations were done using Microsoft excel Spreadsheet.

RESULTS

Diversity and abundance of insect species

A total of 418 individuals consisting of 42 insect species, 41 genera belonging to 6 orders and 43 families were recorded from the study area. A total of 275 individual species was recorded on *Avicennia* and 143 individual species were recorded on *Rhizophora*. *Avicennia* had the greater number of insect species (24), while 21 insect species were recorded from *Rhizophora*. Table 1 shows the diversity and abundance of insects species recovered from *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora* in Borikiri. The species

abundance showed that *Musca domestica* and *Chrysomyia chloropyga* were the most numerous with 114 and 26 individuals respectively followed, in a decreasing order, by *Penthimia bella* (23), *Paratrechina sp.* (18), *Ochthera chalybescens* (15), *Fannia sp.* (15), *Chrysomyza Smaragdina* (14), *Aconura instabilis* (14), *Camponotus sp* (13), *Zaprionus vittiger* (13), *Chrysis sp.*(12), *Pantala flavescens* (12), *Aenigmatistes sp.*(11), *Anopheles squamosus* (9), *Pheidole sp* (9), *Pusillus sp.*(8), *Gitona sp.* (7), *Winthemia anadrata* (7), *Eudorylus sp* (7), *Siphilus sp.*(6), *Elasmosomus sp.*(5), *Tomosvaryella subvirescens* (5), *Brumoides fondrasi* (5), *Hemerodromia sp.* (5), *Trirhithrum sp.* (5), *Lucilia sp.*(5), *Chaetocnema sp.*(4), *Megaselia sp.* (4), *Elasmosomus sp.* (4), *Pteronemobius massaicus* (4), *Elassogaster brachialis* (4), *Ablabesmyia appendiculata* (3), *Leucophenga dilitata* (3), *Plastophora sp* (3), *Carpotheromyia sp.* (3), *Paradalspsis sp.*(3), *Palpomyia pistiae* (2), *Isomyia nitida* (1), *Clinitanypus rugosus* (1), *Elachiptereicus abessynicus* (1), *Acrodesmia illuscens* (1) and *Tinda sp* (1).

Relative abundance of insect species

Musca domestica had the highest relative abundance (27.27%), followed by *Chrysomyia chloropyga* (6.22%), *Penthimia bella* (5.50%), *Paratrechina sp.* (4.30%), *Ochthera chalybescens* (1.91%), *Fannia sp.* (3.58%), *Chrysomyza Smaragdina* (3.34%), *Aconura instabilis* (3.34%), *Camponotus sp* (3.11%), *Zaprionus vittiger* (3.11%), *Chrysis sp.* (2.87%), *Pantala flavescens* (2.87%), *Aenigmatistes sp.* (2.63%), *Anopheles squamosus* (2.15%), *Pheidole sp* (2.15%), *Pusillus sp.* (1.91%), *Gitona sp.* (1.67%), *Winthemia anadrata* (1.67%), *Eudorylus sp* (1.67%), *Siphilus sp.* (1.43%), *Elasmosomus sp.* (1.19%), *Tomosvaryella subvirescens* (1.19%), *Brumoides fondrasi* (1.19%), *Hemerodromia sp.* (1.19%), *Trirhithrum sp.* (1.19%), *Lucilia sp.* (1.19%), *Chaetocnema sp.* (0.95%), *Megaselia sp.* (0.95%), *Elasmosomus sp.* (0.95%), *Pteronemobius massaicus* (0.95%), *Elassogaster brachialis* (0.95%), *Ablabesmyia appendiculata* (0.71%), *Leucophenga dilitata* (0.71%), *Plastophora sp* (0.71%), *Carpotheromyia sp.* (0.71%), *Paradalspsis sp.* (0.71%), *Palpomyia pistiae* (0.47%), *Isomyia nitida* (0.23%), *Clinitanypus rugosus* (0.23%), *Elachiptereicus abessynicus* (0.23%), *Acrodesmia illuscens* (0.23%) and *Tinda sp* (0.23%).

Relative abundance of insect orders

The percentage abundance of mangrove insect orders found at Borikiri is presented in Figure 2. The order Diptera contributed 80% of the insect abundance, followed in a decreasing order by Hymenoptera (9%), Homoptera (5%), Coleoptera (3%), Odonata (2%) and Orthoptera (1%).

Relative abundance of insect families found on *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora*

The percentage abundance of the different families recorded from *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora* (Table 2) shows that a total number of 26 families were found. 24 different families were found and recorded in *Avicennia* with Formicidae, Tephritidae, Cicadellidae, Calliphoridae having the highest percentage abundance of (8%), followed by Stratiomyiidae, Phoridae, Ephydriidae, Muscidae, with (5%) and Coccinelidae, Chrysomelidae, Chrysidae, Ulidiidae, Chironomidae, Plastomatidae, Pipunculidae, Drosophilidae, Empididae, Ceratopogonidae, Libellulidae, Gryllidae, Syrphidae, Tachinidae, Culicidae with (3%). Six (6) families were recorded in *Rhizophora*. The families with the highest abundance were Calliphoridae, Drosophilidae and Muscidae (18%), whereas the remaining families all had percentage abundance of (9%) each. Only 6 families Calliphoridae, Pipunculidae, Drosophilidae, Culicidae,

Phoridae and Muscidae were found in both *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora* were the highest abundance of (18%) were recorded in Calliphoridae, Drosophilidae and Muscidae found in *Rhizophora*.

Diversity indices of insect orders

The order Diptera insects had the highest relative abundance on *Avicennia* (43.8%) followed by Hemiptera (10.3%), Hymenoptera (7.6%), and Odonata (2.95%). No insect species were recorded for Coleoptera and Orthoptera. From *Rhizophora*, Diptera had the highest relative abundance (29.8%), followed by Coleoptera (2.21%), Hymenoptera (2.21%) and Orthoptera (0.98%). No insect species were recorded for Odonata and Homoptera. The diversity indices shows that Dipteran insects have the highest diversity index ($H' = 2.91$) for *Avicennia*, while Coleoptera and Hymenoptera had the highest diversity index ($H' = 1.74$) for *Rhizophora*. Odonata had the highest species richness ($d = 0.40$) for *Avicennia* and Orthoptera had the highest species richness ($d = 0.72$) for *Rhizophora*. Homoptera had the highest evenness index ($E' = 0.76$) for *Avicennia*. However, Coleoptera and Hymenoptera had the highest evenness index ($E' = 0.79$) for *Rhizophora*. Table 3 shows the diversity indices of insect orders recorded on *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora*.

Relationship between temperature, humidity and insect population

The mean temperature was 29.6 ± 0.7 and the humidity was 82 ± 6.4 . The relationship between Temperature and Relative humidity with abundance of insects (Figure 3 and 4) shows that temperature is positively correlated with abundance, while Relative humidity is negatively correlated with abundance. The association between Temperature and Relative humidity with abundance is not significantly correlated ($P > 0.05$). The result also shows that there is a weak relationship between Relative humidity and abundance ($r = 0.1250$) and the relationship between Temperature and Abundance is high ($r = 0.60$).

DISCUSSION

A total of six (6) insect orders were recorded in this study. The order Diptera was the most abundant insect order. This may be due to their ubiquitous nature (Victor and Onomivbpri, 1996) and their preference for lentic habitats during their early stage of life and for breeding purposes (Majunder *et al.*, 2011). This finding is in disagreement with the report of Rahaman (2002), who reported Lepidoptera as the most dominant insect order in Muthupet Mangrove, India. This discrepancy may be due to the difference in floristic composition which is important for pollination and also differences in weather and environmental conditions. In the present study, Hymenoptera was the second most abundant insect order. This may be due to their ability to inhabit different habitats (Sharkey, 2007). Twenty four insect families were found in the different sites, this finding varies from other findings from other Mangrove ecosystems. Mitra *et al.* (2016) reported fifteen insect families in India, Pragrom (2004) reported reported thirty-two families in Bangpakong River in Thailand.

The most abundant family in this research was Formicidae. This may be due to the availability of food sources and favourable environmental factors (Balog and Marko, 2007). In contrast to this finding, Senthil and Varadharajan (1995) reported the family Nymphalidae as the most dominant in Himalaya, Kilbury; Senthil (1992) reported Chironomidae as the most abundant family in Bangladesh.

Species Assemblage

The results obtained from the study revealed an enormous array of insects inhabiting the mangrove ecosystem sampled. A total of forty four insect species were collected from this study. This result varies from the findings of other researchers. Mitra *et al.*, 2016, reported twenty-nine species in India. Rahaman, 2002, reported one hundred and thirteen insect species, only two species (i.e. *Chaetocnema* and *Camponotus spp.*) of these were reported in this study. The presences of *Tabanus*, *Culex* and *Aedes* reported in this study was also reported by Naskar and Guhabakshi (1987) in Sunderbans, Australia. Wahizatul and Lim, 2013, studied Dipterian species diversity and their succession on Rabbit carrion in two different mangrove areas of Peninsular Malaysia and reported 11 species. Amongst the dipterian species found in their research, *Musca domestica*, *Fannia sp.*, and the genera *Chrysomya* were also found in the present research.

Diversity indices showed that Hemiptera was the most diverse on *Avicennia* (Shannon $H' = 2.870$) which is converse with the report of Balakrishnan *et al.* 2014 who reported high diversity of Coleopterans in tropical environments. The order Hymenoptera recorded highest species richness on *Rhizophora* (0.792) which is in agreement with the report of Ojija (2016) who reported high species richness of Hymenoptera on grass land in Tanzania.

Climatic and weather changes have been reported to not only affect the status of insects but also affect their population dynamics, distribution, abundance, intensity and feeding behavior (Khaliq *et al.*, 2014). In this study, temperature was positively correlated with the abundance of insect; hence it was a major determinant of the population of insects in the study area. The temperature values 29.6 ± 0.7 recorded in the study area could be the reason for the high abundance and diversity of the insects. This assertion is in agreement with the several reports in this region (Eyo *et al.*, 2014; Ojianwuna, 2015), which showed that the temperature affects insects abundance positively.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the result obtained from this study revealed the taxonomic richness and variation of insect species in mangrove ecosystem along the Bonny River, which agrees with most studies around the world. The most abundant insect species belong to the order Diptera, with the family Formicidae as the most abundant insect family. From this study, the abundance of the insects could be predicted from temperature. Shannon diversity index was high for only the insect orders Diptera and Hemiptera. However, richness index and evenness was low for all the insect orders on *Avicennia* and *Rhizophora*. This is attributed to anthropogenic impact from the destruction and degradation of mangrove ecosystem. There is therefore urgent need to continuously protect mangrove ecosystems as the continuous destruction and discharge of industrial effluent and organic waste from anthropogenic activities poses a potential threat to insects which can lead to the extinction of insects. The study provides additional baseline information for many environmental assessments that are currently ongoing without relevant information on mangrove insects.

Further studies on the diversity of insect species in mangrove ecosystems within the Niger delta area should be encouraged. Anthropogenic disturbances of mangrove ecosystems should be curtailed in order to conserve the ecosystems and the insect biodiversity they maintain.

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FIGURES

Fig. 1: Map showing Study Location

Fig. 2: Relative Abundance of Insect Orders

Fig. 3: Relationship between Temperature and Insect Population

Fig. 4: Relationship between Relative Humidity and Insect Population

TABLES

Table 1: Diversity and Abundance of Insect Species in the Study Area

Order	Family	Species	<i>Avicennia</i>	<i>Rhizophora</i>	Total	
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chaetocnema</i> <i>sp.</i>	0	4	4	
	Elateridae	<i>Elasmosomus</i> <i>sp.</i>	0	5	5	
Diptera	Calliphoridae	<i>Chrysomyia</i> <i>chloropyga</i>	26	0	26	
		<i>Isomyia</i> <i>evanida</i>	0	4	4	
		<i>Isomyia</i> <i>nitida</i>	0	1	1	
		<i>Lucilia</i> <i>sp.</i>	0	5	5	
	Ceratopogonidae	<i>Palpomyia</i> <i>pistiae</i>	0	2	2	
	Chironomidae	<i>Ablabesmyia</i> <i>rugosus</i> <i>Freeman</i>	0	3	3	
		Chloropidae	<i>Elachiptereicus</i> <i>abessynicus</i>	0	1	1
			<i>Siphilus</i> <i>sp.</i>	6	0	6
	Culicidae	<i>Anopheles</i> <i>squamosus</i>	4	5	9	
	Drosophilidae	<i>Gitona</i> <i>sp.</i>	7	0	7	
		<i>Leucophenga</i> <i>dilitata</i>	0	3	3	
		<i>Zaprionus</i> <i>vittiger</i>	0	13	13	
	Empididae	<i>Hemerodromia</i> <i>sp.</i>	0	5	5	
Ephydriidae	<i>Ochthera</i> <i>chalybescens</i>	8	0	8		
Muscidae	<i>Fannia</i> <i>sp.</i>	9	6	15		
	<i>Musca</i> <i>domestica</i>	65	49	114		

	Phoridae	<i>Aenigmatistes sp.</i>	0	11	11
		<i>Megaselia sp.</i>	0	4	4
		<i>Plastophora sp.</i>	0	3	3
	Pipunculidae	<i>Eudorylus sp.</i>	7	0	7
		<i>Tomosvaryella subvirescens</i>	0	5	5
	Platstomatidae	<i>Elassogaster brachialis</i>	4	0	4
	Stratiomyiidae	<i>Acrodesmia illuscens</i>	1	0	1
		<i>Tinda sp.</i>	1	0	1
	Syrphidae	<i>Pusillus sp.</i>	8	0	8
	Tachinidae	<i>Winthemia anadrata</i>	7	0	7
		<i>Carpothoromyia sp.</i>	3	0	3
		<i>Paradalspsis sp.</i>	3	0	3
			5	0	5
	Ulidiidae	<i>Chrysomyza smaragdina</i>	14	0	14
Homoptera	Cicadellidae	<i>Brumoides fondrasi</i>	5	0	5
		<i>Aconura instabilis</i>	14	0	14
		<i>Penthimia bella</i>	23	0	23
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Camponotus sp.</i>	13	0	13
		<i>Paratrechina sp.</i>	18	0	18
		<i>Pheidole sp.</i>	0	9	9
	Chrysidae	<i>Chrysis sp.</i>	12	0	12
Odonata	Libellulidae	<i>Pantala flavescens</i>	12	0	12
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Pteronemobius massaicus</i>	0	4	4

Table 2: Relative Abundance of Insect Species from the Study Area

Species	Relative Abundance %
<i>Ablabesmyia appendiculata</i> Kieffer	0.71
<i>Aconura instabilis</i> Ribaut	3.34
<i>Acrodesmia illuscens</i> Linn	0.23
<i>Aenigmatistes</i> sp.	2.63
<i>Anopheles squamosus</i> Theobald	2.15
<i>Brumoides fondrasi</i> Mulsant	1.19
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. Nr. Perrisi. For	3.11
<i>Carpothoromyia</i> sp.	0.71
<i>Chaetocnema</i> sp.	0.95
<i>Chrysis</i> sp.	2.87
<i>Chrysomyia chloropyga</i> Wied	6.22
<i>Chrysomyza smaragdina</i> Loen	3.34
<i>Clinitanypus rugosus</i> Freeman	0.23
<i>Elachiptereicus abessynicus</i> Becker	0.23
<i>Elasmosomus</i> sp.	1.19
<i>Elassogaster brachialis</i> Rond	0.95
<i>Eudorylus</i> sp.	1.67
<i>Fannia</i> sp.	3.58
<i>Gitona</i> sp.	1.67
<i>Hemerodromia</i> sp.	1.19
<i>Isomyia evanida</i> Ville	0.95
<i>Isomyia nitida</i> Cumin	0.23
<i>Leucophenga dilitata</i> Bachii	0.71
<i>Lucilia</i> sp.	1.19
<i>Megaselia</i> sp.	0.95
<i>Musca domestica</i>	27.27
<i>Ochthera chalybescens</i> Loen	1.91
<i>Palpomyia pistiae</i> Ingram & Motic	0.47
<i>Pantala flavescens</i> Fab	2.87
<i>Paradaspsis</i> sp.	0.71
<i>Paratrechina</i> sp.	4.30
<i>Penthimia bella</i> Stal	5.50
<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	2.15
<i>Plastophora</i> sp.	0.71
<i>Pteronemobius massaicus</i> Sjostedi	0.95
<i>Pusillus</i> sp.	1.91
<i>Siphilus</i> sp.	1.43
<i>Tinda</i> sp.	0.23

<i>Tomosvaryella subvirescens</i>	1.19
<i>Trirhithrum</i> sp.	1.19
<i>Winthemia anadrata</i> Wied	1.67
<i>Zaprionus vittiger</i> Coq	3.11

Table 3: Percentage Abundance of the Different Families in the Study Area

Family	Frequency	Percentage
* Cicadellidae	3	8%
* Stratiomyiidae	2	5%
* Phoridae	2	5%
* Coccinelidae	1	3%
* Formicidae	3	8%
* Tephritidae	3	8%
* Chrysomelidae	1	3%
* Chrysidae	1	3%
* Calliphoridae	3	8%
* Ulidiidae	1	3%
* Chironomidae	1	3%
* Chloropidae	2	5%
* Platstomatidae	1	3%
* Pipunculidae	1	3%
* Drosophilidae	1	3%
* Empididae	1	3%
* Ephydriidae	2	5%
* Ceratopogonidae	1	3%
* Libellulidae	1	3%
* Gryllidae	1	3%
* Syrphidae	1	3%
* Tachinidae	1	3%
* Muscidae	2	5%
* Culicidae	1	3%
** Chironomidae	1	9%
** Elateridae	1	9%
** Calliphoridae	2	18%
** Drosophilidae	2	18%
** Phoridae	1	9%
** Pipunculidae	1	9%
** Muscidae	2	18%
** Culicidae	1	9%

* Avicennia

**Rhizophora

Table 4: Diversity Indices for the Different Insect Orders in Borikiri

Order	Plant	Number of Species	Abundance	Shannon Weiner	Margalef index	Evenness index
Diptera	<i>Avicennia</i>	17	178	2.816	0.193	0.543
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	17	121	1.414	0.209	0.295
Coleoptera	<i>Avicennia</i>	0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	2	9	1.741	0.455	0.792
Hemiptera	<i>Avicennia</i>	3	42	2.870	0.268	0.768
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hymenoptera	<i>Avicennia</i>	2	31	2.461	0.291	0.717
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	1	9	1.741	0.455	0.792
Orthoptera	<i>Avicennia</i>	0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	1	4	1.000	0.721	0.722
Odonata	<i>Avicennia</i>	1	12	1.367	0.402	0.550
	<i>Rhizophora</i>	0	0	0.000	0.000	0.000